

This article is made available by the Document Delivery Service of IRRI Library for personal scholarly, research, and educational use. Further distribution requires the permission of the copyright owner.

Variation in RFLP markers associated with root-growth QTLs in Indian upland rice

K.A. Steele, B.J. Moore, J.R. Witcombe, and D.S. Virk, Centre of Arid Zone Studies, University of Wales, Bangor, LL57 2UW; and A.H. Price, Department of Plant and Soil Science, University of Aberdeen, Cruickshank Building, Aberdeen, AB24 3UU, UK E-mail: k.a.steele@bangor.ac.uk

Kalinga III, bred at the Central Rice Research Institute in Cuttack, is an improved variety popular in drought-prone areas of India. It normally escapes the end-of-season drought because of its extreme earliness, but it is drought-susceptible. Sathi 34-36, an improved variety from Gujarat, India, derived from landraces, has longer and thicker roots than Kalinga III. Quantitative trait loci (QTLs) influencing root length and thickness in rice have been identified in previous studies (Price and Tomos 1996, Price et al 2000, Yadav et al 1997). Molecular markers located near QTLs may correlate with the same trait in different varieties, and these markers could be used in marker-assisted selection (MAS) to improve drought-sensitive varieties. Restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) markers on chromosomes with root QTLs were used to compare genetic variation within and between Indian landraces and improved varieties.

Sixteen rice varieties were screened with 55 RFLP probes (from chromosomes 2, 5, 7, 8, 9, and 11), 14 of which were linked to QTLs for root growth. Four varieties were landraces and six were released varieties derived from landraces, all widely grown in India (see table). Other varieties which have been used for mapping were included: Azucena (japonica), Bala (indica, an Aus variety), CO 39 (indica), and Moroberekan (japonica).

DNA extraction and RFLP analysis were carried out as described in Price et al (2000). Five restriction enzymes were tested and polymorphic bands were scored for presence or absence in all 16 varieties. Data were analyzed by cluster analysis using SPSS (version 8). Similarity was estimated using Jaccard's coefficient. Hierarchical clustering was performed on

the squared Euclidean distance matrix to produce a dendrogram.

Twelve probes gave no polymorphisms while 43 probes gave 110 scorable polymorphic bands (30 of which have been mapped in the Bala/Azucena F_6 population). Cluster analysis using all 110 polymorphic markers separated indicas from japonicas (see figure). Average linkage and single linkage gave similar results. Simi-

larity ranged from $82 \pm 4\%$ between Azucena and Moroberekan to $19 \pm 4\%$ between Azucena and Bala. The four Indian landraces and Sathi 34-36 grouped together and were separated from the improved varieties (Sathi 34-36 and Kalinga III had only $37 \pm 5\%$ similarity). Despite being geographically diverse, the landraces were similar at many marker loci and were less diverse than improved varieties (e.g.,

Indian varieties used in molecular marker studies.

Germplasm	Desirable trait	Type	Basis of selection
Kalinga III	Earliness, medium-tall plants, fine grains, good cooking quality	Released for uplands in Orissa	Most farmer-preferred variety in participatory varietal selection in India. ^{a,b} Most widely adopted in drought-prone uplands
IR36	High yield, stiff straw	Released variety for irrigated environments	High yield, multiple resistances
IR64	High yield, fine grain	Released variety for irrigated environments	High yield, multiple resistances
Sathi 34-36	High yield, stiff straw, long roots, drought tolerance	Released variety in Gujarat (derived from a landrace)	Performance in western ^a India
Nanisal	Drought resistance, delayed senescence	Landrace	Performance in western ^a India
Vaghardha	Grain quality	Released variety for Banswara area of Rajasthan	Performance in on-station trials
Vandana	High yield, earliness, long roots, drought resistance	Released for uplands in India	Performance in farmers' field trials in western ^a and eastern ^b India
Yanprabha	High yield, earliness, long roots, drought resistance	Released for uplands in India	Performance in farmers' field trials in eastern ^b India
Birsa Dhan 102	Earliness, drought resistance, long roots	Released in Bihar, developed by selection from a local landrace of upland rice, Brown Gora	Performance in farmers' field trials in eastern ^b India
Dabra	Earliness, drought resistance	Landrace in western India	Observations in farmers' fields in western ^a India
Ratta Chawal	Drought resistance, stiff straw, tall plants	Landrace in western India	Observations in farmers' fields in western ^a India
Pathara	Drought resistance, earliness	Landrace in western India	Observations in farmers' fields in western ^a India

^aData from KRIBP (W): Krishak Bharati Co-operative Indo-British Rainfed Farming Project, West. ^bData from KRIBP (E): Krishak Bharati Co-operative Indo-British Rainfed Farming Project, East.

Dabra and Pathara shared $73 \pm 4\%$ similarity). Cluster analysis using only the 14 mapped markers linked to QTLs for root traits gave identical first- and second-level groups, as did analysis using only 16 mapped markers not linked to root QTLs. A further 34 markers, covering all 12 chromosomes, were screened on the two released varieties, Kalinga III and Sathi 34-36; 66% of them were polymorphic.

In the mapping population derived from Bala/Azucena, Azucena was the donor of positive alleles for four QTLs, while Bala was the donor for one QTL on chromosome 5. Kalinga III had the Bala-type locus for nine markers at QTLs on chromosomes 2, 7, 9, and 11. Because most Indian landraces had the Azucena locus in up to five of these markers, they could be used as donor parents for MAS to improve Kalinga III for root growth. Dabra, Ratta Chawal, and Sathi 34-36 had the Azucena allele at markers C601 (chromosome 2), RG650 (chromosome 7), and RG2 (chromosome 11).

Acknowledgment

This document is an output from a project funded by the UK Department for Inter-

national Development (DfID) (project No. R7080, Plant Sciences Programme) for the benefit of developing countries. The views expressed are not necessarily those of DfID.

References

Price AH, Steele KA, Moore BJ, Barraclough PB, Clarke LJ. 2000. A combined RFLP and AFLP linkage map of upland rice (*Oryza sativa* L.)

used to identify QTLs for root penetration ability. *Theor. Appl. Genet.* (in press)
 Price AH, Tomos AD. 1996. Genetic dissection of root growth in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.). II: Mapping quantitative trait loci using molecular markers. *Theor. Appl. Genet.* 95:143–152.
 Yadav R, Courtois B, Huang N, McLaren G. 1997. Mapping genes controlling root morphology and root distribution on a double-haploid population of rice. *Theor. Appl. Genet.* 96:619–632.

Dendrogram showing hierarchical (average linkage, between-group) clustering of varieties based on 110 RFLP bands.

Evaluation of *in situ* conservation of *Oryza rufipogon* populations using RAPD markers

Z.-W. Xie, S. Ge, K.-Q. Wang, D.-Y. Hong, Laboratory of Systematic and Evolutionary Botany, Institute of Botany, Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS), Beijing 100093; and B.R. Lu, GRC, IRRI E-mail: xiezw@public.east.cn.net

Oryza rufipogon Griff. is a perennial species widely distributed in the tropics and subtropics of monsoon Asia. It constitutes a valuable genetic resource for rice improvement (Chang 1984). This species once occurred in eight provinces and autonomous regions of China but it is now extinct in Fujian and is nearly extinct in Hunan and Jiangxi. An intensive biodiversity conservation program for *O. rufipogon* has recently been initiated in China, using the *in situ* approach, which has been regarded as an effective method

to maintain diversity of wild rice species in their original habitats (Vaughan and Chang 1992). Knowledge on genetic diversity, population structure, and dynamics of the target *O. rufipogon* populations is important for strategic design and effective management and conservation. Such information, however, is still very limited. This study aimed to estimate the genetic diversity of *O. rufipogon* populations and to confirm the *in situ* conservation sites for this species using random amplified polymorphic DNA (RAPD) markers.

Six *O. rufipogon* populations from *in situ* conservation sites in China were investigated through field surveys during 1997-98. These populations were classified into four groups according to their origins (Table 1). Young and clean leaves of 15–18 individuals were sampled from different populations (Table 1). The method for sample collection, leaf preservation, and DNA extraction followed those described by Xie et al (1999). To prevent overestimating the genetic diversity by polymorphic loci variation, 20 primers (OPB 1–20